

Project acronym: SURE-Farm

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D7.4 Mid-term and final scientific seminar

Work Performed by Partner's No 9., Universidad Politécnica de Madrid

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1 The SURE- Farm mid-term scientific seminar

The mid-term scientific seminar took place the 26th September the 2019 in Bucharest organized by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (P9) in close collaboration with Wageningen University and Research (P1) and the Institute of Agricultural Economics of the Romanian Academy (P13). The mid-term seminar was scheduled under the 173rd EAAE seminar, “Sustainable and resilient farming systems in the European Union”, organized by the Institute of Agricultural Economics of the Romanian Academy in cooperation with the Romanian Association of Rural and Agri-Food Economy "Virgil Madgearu".

Two keynote speakers opened the scientific seminar in the one-hour plenary session: Ika Darnhofer from the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna and Miranda Meuwissen, SURE-Farm coordinator, from the Wageningen University and Research. The plenary session was held in the Romanian Academy.

Then, the SURE-Farm partners presented the results achieved so far in the different topics addressed in the project. All the presentations followed similar structure built on the farming system resilience framework to better guide the audience through the different research’s achievements. The presentations took place in the Hotel Ambassador (panoramic room).

The number of people attending the mid-term scientific plenary session and presentation sessions varies between 25-45 persons.

The mid-term scientific seminar program was the following:

11:20– 12:30	Plenary Session: Ika Darnhofer (University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna) – “On the theoretical challenges to assess the resilience of farms” Miranda Meuwissen (Wageningen University and Research) – “Resilience of EU farming systems; how to measure a multi-dimensional concept?”
12:30– 13:30	<i>Lunch</i>
13:30– 15:00	Session 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perceived resilience across European Union farms. Spiegel et al. (WUR) • The role of learning in adapting to changes – a case study regarding the small mixed farms in Nord-Est region of Romania. Tudor et al. (IEA-AR) • Evaluating the role of agricultural risk management in strengthening farming systems’ resilience; results from co-creation approaches. Soriano et al. (UPM). • Understanding European farm demographic change processes and influencing factors: qualitative findings from a multiple case-study approach. Coopmans et al. (ILVO).

15:00– 15:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
15:30– 17:00	<p>Session 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do the CAP and its national implementations enable or constrain the resilience of farming systems in the European Union? A comparative assessment. Feindt et al. (Humboldt University) • How effective is the CAP at stimulating generational renewal? Pitson et al. (IAMO) • A dynamic perspective to farming resilience and its trade-offs. Herrera et al. (University of Bergen) • Participatory impact assessment of sustainability and resilience across farming systems in the European Union. Paas et al. (WUR).

The mid-term seminar was recorded with the aim at editing shorts videos to be uploaded to the website and social media. Indeed, participants in the mid-term seminar was interviewed and recorded: Ika Darnhofer, Miranda Meuwissen, Peter Feindt, and Isabeau Coopmans. The short-video interviews edited and posted on the SURE-Farm website and social media to extend the impact of the seminar.

1.1 The communication of the mid-term scientific seminar

1.1.1 Communication activities before the mid-term scientific seminar

The mid-term seminar was announced on the SURE-Farm website :

The screenshot shows the SURE-Farm website with a news article titled "SURE-Farm mid-term scientific seminar" dated 18th July 2019. The article text states: "The SURE-Farm mid-term scientific seminar will take place during the 173rd EAAE Seminar of the European Association of Agricultural Economists in Bucharest. It aims at presenting the main results to date of the project. Topics covered will include the risk behavior, risk management and resilience, learning capacity, farm demographics, agricultural policies and impact assessment. The seminar will welcome Miranda Meuwissen (WUR), coordinator of the SURE-Farm project and Ika Darnhofer (BOKU), member of the SURE-Farm International Scientific Committee. Click here to have access to the agenda: [Agenda SURE-Farm mid-term scientific seminar](#)".

On the right side of the screenshot, there is a sidebar with a "RELEASE CALENDAR" section. It includes a "Release calendar" link, a "Press Release on Resilience Framework" link (noted as translated into 11 languages), and a link for those interested in receiving more information about SURE-Farm. Below this is a yellow box with the EAAE logo and the text "SURE-Farm mid-term scientific seminar" and "26th September, Bucharest (Romania)". A "Summary" section follows, providing details about the seminar's location and topics.

And on the SURE-Farm social media (Twitter and Instagram) :

A dedicated banner was designed to be posted to the 173rd EAAE seminar website:

A roll-up was designed for the presentation and interviews recording.

The SURE-Farm flyers were available in the 173rd EAAE seminar to inform participants about SURE-Farm project.

1.1.2 Communication activities during the mid-term scientific seminar

Mid-term seminar presentations were posted on social media in real time. See below some examples:

1.1.3 Communication activities after the mid-term scientific seminar

Presentation slides, videos and interviews will be edited and uploaded to the SURE-farm website and posted on the social media. A dedicated tab is available on the SURE-Farm website to upload all this information.

Presentations

SURE-Farm Mid-term Scientific Seminar

[Agenda SURE-Farm mid-term scientific seminar](#)

[On theoretical challenges to assess the resilience of farms and farming systems. Ika Darnhofer, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences.](#)

[Resilience of farming systems; how to measure a multi-dimensional concept. Miranda Meuwissen, Wageningen University and Research.](#)

[Perceived resilience capacities across EU farmers. Alisa Spiegel, Wageningen University and Research.](#)

[Understanding European farm demographic change processes and influencing factors – qualitative findings from a multiple case study approach. Isabeau Coopmans, Instituut Voor Landbouw En Visserijonderzoek, ILVO.](#)

[The role of agricultural risk management in strengthening farming systems' resilience: Results from a multi-scale co-creation approach. Bárbara Soriano, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid.](#)

[Role of learning in adapting to changes. A case study regarding the small mixed farms in Nord-Est region of Romania. Monica-Mihaela Tudor, Institute of Agricultural Economics, Romanian Academy, Romania](#)

[How do the CAP and its national implementations enable or constrain the resilience of farming systems in the European Union? A comparative assessment. Peter H. Feindt, Humboldt University at Berlin](#)

[Generational Renewal and European agriculture: a resilience analysis from agent based simulations. Christine Pitson, Leibniz-Institut für Agrarentwicklung in Transformationsökonomien, IAMO.](#)

[A dynamic perspective to farming system resilience and its trade-offs. Hugo Herrera, University of Bergen](#)

[Participatory impact assessment of sustainability and resilience across farming systems in the European](#)

Video

[On theoretical challenges to assess the resilience of farms and farming systems, Ika Darnhofer](#)

[Resilience of farming systems; how to measure a multi-dimensional concept, Miranda Meuwissen](#)

[Perceived resilience capacities across EU farmers, Alisa Spiegel](#)

[Understanding European farm demographic change processes and influencing factors, Isabeau Coopmans](#)

[Role of learning in adapting to changes, Monica-Mihaela Tudor](#)

[The role of agricultural risk management in strengthening farming systems' resilience, Bárbara Soriano](#)

[How do the CAP enable the resilience of farming systems in the European Union?, Peter Feindt](#)

[Generational Renewal and European agriculture, Christine Pitson](#)

[A dynamic perspective to farming system resilience and its trade-offs, Hugo Herrera](#)

2 The final scientific seminar

The final scientific seminar was held online the 18th May 2021 organized by the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (P9) in close collaboration with Wageningen University and Reserch (P1). The mid-term seminar was scheduled under the 178th EAAE seminar, Future challenges and resilience of farming systems in Europe. 94 attendees joint the SURE-Farm final seminar.

A dedicated online platform was designed and created to host the scientific seminar. The access to the platform was free, previous registration. Different rooms were available for the attendees:

The lobby

The Auditorium

The networking and the support rooms.

The SURE-Farm final seminar was opened by Miranda Meuwissen, SURE-Farm coordinator followed by the keynote speaker, Katharina Helming from Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF). Then, the SURE-Farm partners presented pitches about take-home messages regarding the different disciplines addressed in SURE-Farm: risk management, policy, demographics, integrated impact and roadmaps. Finally, a specific session was organized to give a voice to the stakeholders who have been participating in the SURE-farm co-creation platform to get the insights from the field. The final seminar was recorded.

Final scientific seminar agenda

	Topic	Presenter	Chair
Tuesday 18 May			
9.00 Room A	SURE-Farm approach to assess the resilience of Europe's diverse farming systems	Miranda Meuwissen, Wageningen University	Miranda Meuwissen
9.15 Room A	Keynote "Future agricultural management conditions – perceptions and pathways" [30 min + 15 min Q]	Katharina Helming, Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research (ZALF)	
10.00	BREAK (Networking room)		
10.15	SURE-Farm Final video		Miranda Meuwissen
10.20 Room A	SURE-Farm Pitches & Questions: 3 key findings [max 3 slides] & 3 questions from the audience [3 min pitch, 4 min for Q, 1 min for change]		Miranda Meuwissen
	- Farm demographic issues with regard to resilience; the way forward	Alfons Balmann, IAMO	
	- The role of policy; enhancing or constraining resilience?	Peter Feindt, Humboldt University at Berlin; Katrien Termeer, Wageningen University	

	Topic	Presenter	Chair
	- Integrated resilience assessments; what do they reveal about the resilience of farming systems in Europe?	Pytrik Reidsma, Wageningen University	
	- Roadmaps to enhance resilience; the role of farming systems actors and the enabling environment	Erwin Wauters, ILVO; Erik Mathijs, KU Leuven	
	- Diverse case studies: what did we learn from the diversity in Europe?	Kasia Zawalińska, Polish Academy of Sciences	
	- The contribution of risk management to the resilience of farming systems	Robert Finger, ETH Zurich	
	- Applying the SURE-Farm approach to Covid-19; lessons learned	Miranda Meuwissen	
11.15	BREAK (Networking room)		
11.30 Room A	Short reflections from the field [3 points per speaker, questions at the end]	Rob Wessels, Bakker Barendrecht; Michiel Klompenhouwer, Rabobank; Sebastian Mahler, GVF Insurance; Inés Isabel la Moneda, MAPA; Koert Verkerk, FrieslandCampina	Bárbara Soriano
12.15 Room A	The way forward	Miranda Meuwissen	
12.30	Closure day 1		

2.1 The communication of the final scientific seminar

2.1.1 Communication activities before the final scientific seminar

Information about the SURE-Farm final seminar was posted on the 178th EAAE seminar:

← → ↻ 178eaaeseminar.org

OBJECTIVES

The EAAE seminar aims to offer an interactive platform to exchange ideas and to generate an integrated view of adjustments and prospects in resilience of farming systems in Europe. The seminar is relevant to the scientific community and to decision makers in business, politics and NGO including the donor community.

The seminar intends to discuss and analyse the state-of-the-art in future challenges identification and resilience assessment in European agriculture. What are the major challenges for farming systems in the future? What farming systems are able to cope with the challenges? What are the promising strategies in enhancing future resilience capacities? What role should policy makers, farmers, and other stakeholders play towards more resilient farming systems? This includes quantitative and qualitative analyses of expectations and perceptions of farming system agents, (new) risk management strategies, changing supply chains and interactions between stakeholders. It also includes policy research on enabling resilience capacities through the CAP.

The SURE-Farm final scientific seminar will take place the 19th May 2021

And on the SURE-Farm website and social media:

TOPICS

Expected topics to be covered by the papers include:

- Quantitative and qualitative assessment of economic, environmental, social and institutional challenges for farming systems in Europe.
- Quantitative and qualitative assessment of resilience-enhancing strategies, policies and system characteristics.
- Farmers' and stakeholders' awareness, knowledge and adoption of (new) resilience-enhancing strategies, including joint learning and innovative insurance, and strategies to improve farm demographics and the availability of skilled labour.
- The role of supply chains in enhancing resilience.
- The role of local, national, and European governments in increasing resilience.

2.1.1 Communication activities during the final scientific seminar

Tweets were posted on tweeter:

2.1.2 Communication activities after the final scientific seminar

Presentations and videos are available on the SURE-Farm website and on the 178th EAAE seminar website:

The screenshot shows the SURE-Farm website interface. At the top left is the SURE Farm logo. To the right are social media icons for Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram, and the text 'INTRANET CO-CREATION PLATFORM'. Below this is a navigation menu with 'PUBLICATIONS' highlighted. A search bar is also present. The main content area is titled 'Presentations' and contains several sections:

- 178th EAAE Online Seminar. Future challenges and resilience of farming systems in Europe**
 - [Description of the 178th EAAE Online Seminar](#)
- Kick-off presentation**
 - [Future challenges and resilience of farming systems In Europe](#)
Miranda Meuwissen & SURE-Farm consortium
- Keynote presentation**
 - [Future Agricultural Management Conditions - Pathways and Perceptions](#)
Katharina Helmig
- SURE-Farm Pitches & Questions**
 - [Future farm demographics and intergenerational renewal in EU farming systems](#)
Alfons Balmann et al.
 - [The role of policy - constraining or enabling resilience?](#)
Peter H. Feindt et al.
 - [Integrated resilience assessments; what do they reveal about the resilience of farming systems in Europe?](#)
Fyrik Reidsma et al.
 - [Towards a resilience enabling environment: principles and roadmaps](#)
Erwin Vauters et al.
 - [Improved Risk Management Towards More Resilient EU Farming Systems](#)
Robert Finjger et al.
 - [Resilience is context-specific, and so are resilience needs in CS farming systems](#)
Katarzyna Zawalińska

Below the presentations section is a 'Video' section with the following links:

- [Summary video](#)
- [Kick-off and keynote presentations](#)
- [SURE-Farm Pitches & Questions](#)
- [Short reflections from the field](#)

Tweets on seminar information were posted:

3 EAAE Webinar

A webinar on SURE-Farm policy recommendations was organized in collaboration with the EAAE the 17th March 2021. 97 people attended the webinar. The webinar was recorded

The program of the webinar was the following:

POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS TO ENHANCE RESILIENCE OF EUROPEAN FARMING SYSTEMS

Date: March 17, 2021

Time: 16.00-17.30 (GMT+1)

Organiser: Bárbara Soriano

Still suffering the consequences of the Covid-19 crisis, resilience has become a major concern for policy making globally and in the European Union. The effects of the crisis on European agricultural and food sector have been far-reaching, including disrupted value chains and lost market access due to closed borders, shut-down of slaughterhouses, closure of restaurants, general income loss, and seasonal workforce unable to travel across borders. Also prior to the Covid-19 crisis, European farming systems had been challenged by climate change and ecological problems, global competition and volatile markets, geo-political uncertainty and trade conflicts, changing consumer preferences and reduced acceptance of intensive farming methods.

This webinar aims to present how public policies affect the resilience of farming systems and to propose policy recommendations for improved resilience.

The webinar consists of four policy-oriented contributions. The first presentation provides policy recommendations to support risk management decision making in EU farming systems. The second policy-oriented contribution delves into farms demographics and intergenerational renewal and provides policy options that may enable resilient farm structures. The third contribution shows a critical analysis of how the current CAP and adjacent policies constrain/enable resilient European agriculture and suggests recommendations for the CAP. The last policy-oriented contribution examines past and future strategies and policy interventions that promote resilient farming systems. The webinar will be closed by an intervention of the DG-Agri and CEJA-Young farmers representatives to share their opinion about how the policy recommendations would work.

Talks (presenters in bold)

Introductory Remarks (5 minutes)

[**Miranda Meuwissen**, Wageningen University and Research]

Policy recommendations

- 1. Farmer adaptive behaviour and risk management in EU agriculture (10 minutes)**
[Robert Finger, Vroege Willemijn, **Miranda Meuwissen**, ann de Mey, Thomas Slijper, Alisa Spiegel, Marijn Poortvliet, Mauro Vigani, Julie Urquhart, Robert Berry, Peter Midmore, Sue Fowler, Pip Nicholas, Isabel Bardají, **Bárbara Soriano**, Alberto Garrido]
- 2. Future farm demographics and intergenerational renewal in EU-farming systems (10 minutes)**
[Christine Pitson, Franziska Appel, **Alfons Balmann**, Isabeau Coopmans, Erwin Wauters]
- 3. Critical analysis of how current policies constrain/enable resilient EU agriculture (10 mins)**
[Jeroen Candel, **Peter Feindt**, Katrien Termeer, Erik Mathijs, Yannick Buitenhuis]
- 4. Resilience of farming systems in the EU under current conditions and future scenarios (10 mins)**
[**Pytrik Reidsma**, Wim Paas, Francesco Accatino, Franziska Appel, Jasmine Black, Jo Bijttebier, Camelia Gavrilesu, Birgit Kopainsky, Vitaliy Krupin, Gordana Manevska Tasevska, Miranda Meuwissen, Franziska Ollendorf, Mariya Peneva, Saverio Senni, Simone Severini, Bárbara Soriano, Julie Urquhart, Mauro Vigani, Katarzyna Zawalinska, Cinzia Zinnanti, Hugo Herrera]

Stakeholders interventions

1. **DG Agri's view about policy recommendations to enhance resilience of farming systems. Reflection on how will CAP 2020 promote farmers resilience (15 mins)**
[Tassos Haniotis, Director, DG Agriculture, European Commission]
2. **Farmers' view about policy recommendations to enhance resilience of farming systems. Reflection on challenges at farm and farmers' capacity to deal with them (15 mins)**
[Marion Picot, Policy Advisor at CEJA Young Farmers]

The webinar was communicated on the SURE-Farm website and social media and on the EAAE website.

Presentations and video recording are available on the SURE-Farm website

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SEARCH

Presentations

Programme

[6th EAAE webinar. Programme.](#)

[Policy brief on farmer adaptive behaviour and risk management in EU agriculture](#)

[Robert Finger](#), [Vroeghe Willemijn](#), [Miranda Meuwissen](#), [Yann de Mey](#), [Thomas Slijper](#), [Alisa Scieggel](#), [Marjin Poortvliet](#), [Mauro Viganì](#), [Julie Urojuhrt](#), [Robert Berry](#), [Peter Midmore](#), [Sue Fowler](#), [Pio Nicholas](#), [Isabel Bardaji](#), [Bárbara Soriano](#), [Alberto Garrido](#)

[Policy Brief on future farm demographics and intergenerational renewal in EU farming systems](#)

[Alfons Balmann](#), [Franziska Appel](#), [Jo Bijttebier](#), [Isabeau Coopmans](#), [Christine Pitson](#), [Julie Urojuhrt](#), [Mauro Viganì](#), [Erwin Wauters](#)

[Policy brief: How the CAP can enable European agriculture's resilience capacities](#)

[Peter H. Feindt](#), [Katrien Termeer](#), [Jeroen Candel](#) and [Yannick Buitenhuis](#), with input from [Alfons Balmann](#), [Isabel Bardaji](#), [François Léger](#), [Ewoud Lievens](#), [Lucian Luca](#), [Gordana Manevska-Tasevska](#), [Anna Martikainen](#), [Erik Mathijs](#), [Peter Midmore](#), [Mariya Peneva](#), [Simone Severini](#), [Bárbara Soriano](#), [Alessandro Sorrentino](#), [Dan-Marius Voicilas](#), [Katarzyna Zewalinska](#)

[Policy Brief on resilience of farming systems in the EU under current conditions and future scenarios](#)

[Pyrrik Reidsma](#), [Wim Paas](#), [Francesco Accatino](#), [Franziska Appel](#), [Jasmine Black](#), [Jo Bijttebier](#), [Camelia Gavrilescu](#), [Birgit Kopainsky](#), [Vitaliy Kravtsov](#), [Gordana Manevska-Tasevska](#), [Miranda Meuwissen](#), [Franziska Ollendorf](#), [Mariya Peneva](#), [Saverio Senni](#), [Simone Severini](#), [Bárbara Soriano](#), [Julie Urojuhrt](#), [Mauro Viganì](#), [Katarzyna Zewalinska](#), [Cinzia Zinnanti](#), [Hugo Herrera](#)

[Recommendations to enhance resilience of farming systems: The perspective of \(young\) farmers](#)

[Marion Picot](#), [Policy Advisor](#), [European Council of Young farmers](#)

Video

[6th EAAE webinar on policy recommendations to enhance resilience of European farming systems](#)

